

Mint Rasgulla: A sweet with medicinal value

Nabonita Pal^{1*}, Maria Fernandes^{2¤}, Sitangshu Roy^{1†}, Jayashree Saha^{3#}, Anubhav Choudhury^{3§},
Indrajit Ghosh^{4Δ}, Chadambetengkam B. Marak^{4◊}, Sufia Zaman^{1¥} and Abhijit Mitra^{5◊}

¹Department of Oceanography, Techno India University, West Bengal, Salt Lake Sector V, Kolkata, 700091, W. B, India.

²School of Management, Techno India University, West Bengal, Salt Lake Sector V, Kolkata, 700091, W. B, India.

³Department of Microbiology, Techno India University, West Bengal, Salt Lake Sector V, Kolkata, 700091, W. B, India.

⁴Department of Mathematics, Techno India University, West Bengal, Salt Lake Sector V, Kolkata, 700091, W. B, India.

⁵Department of Marine Science, University of Calcutta, 35 B.C. Road, Kolkata, 700019, W. B, India.

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Abstract

The proximate analysis and mineral composition of mint (*Mentha piperita*) were studied during June 2019. The mint was collected from Madhyamgram region of North 24 Paraganas district in West Bengal (India). The extract of the leaf was mixed with channa (a milk product) to prepare rasgulla, a famous traditional Indian sweet. The composition of the prepared rasgulla was studied and compared with the control (where the mint leaf extract was not mixed). Significant variations in composition were observed between control and experimental rasgullas. The experimental rasgullas prepared from mint leaf extract were highly rich in potassium, which may be useful to treat people having hypertension.

Keywords: Mint (*Mentha piperita*), Mint rasgulla, Proximate analysis, Mineral composition.

* Email: nabonita.pal2014@gmail.com

¤ Email: maria.aitmc@gmail.com

† Email: isitangshuroy@gmail.com

Email: sahajayashree15@gmail.com

§ Email: anubhavchoudhury46@gmail.com

Δ Email: indrajit.ghosh304@gmail.com

◊ Email: chadambetengkamm@gmail.com

¥ Email: zamansufia123@gmail.com

◊ Email: abhijit_mitra@hotmail.com

1. Introduction

The Indian subcontinent is famous for variety of sweets. For most of the Indians, a major meal without a dessert is of no attraction. Dessert is the best part of the meal, especially if it is a traditional milk-based rasgulla or gulab jamun. There is a wide spectrum of milk-based sweets in India compared to any other countries of the World. Just as Indian cuisine varies from North to South and East to West, sweets also vary from one region to other. However, rasgulla which is a traditional sweet of West Bengal is widely accepted in all corners of the Indian sub-continent. This traditional Indian cheese dessert is highly nutritious as 100 g of rasgulla is equivalent to 213 Kcal calorie energy of which carbohydrate contributes about 50 g, fat about 1.20 g and protein about 4 g. The main ingredients are channa³ [1] and sugar. The soft ball of channa soaked in sugar syrup delights the taste buds of sweet lovers. However to many customers, this sweet ball is a cause of concern as the sweet sugar is the root cause of diabetes. Hence, the diabetic patients usually avoid the consumption of this delicious sweet. There are various types of rasgulla sold in the market. This includes ordinary sugar mixed with rasgulla, spongy rasgulla and even diabetic rasgulla. Spongy rasgulla differs in terms of taste, texture and succulence as compared to ordinary rasgulla. The diabetic rasgulla is prepared by replacing sucrose with low calorie sweeteners or alcoholic sugar such as sorbitol to cater the need of the people suffering from diabetes. In Northern India, the dish comes flavoured in saffron, rose water and sometimes garnished with chopped pistachious. When orange extract is added with channa, then the sweet is known as Kamala Bhog.

³Chhana is an acid coagulated product obtained from milk. The curd mass obtained when milk is coagulated with the organic acids such as citric acid, lactic acid at higher temperature and after subsequent drainage of whey, mass of curd obtained is called *chhana*. It looks off-white, tastes mildly acidic, and has characteristic spongy texture.

According to FSSR-1511 *chhana* means the product obtained from the cow or buffalo milk or a combination thereof by precipitation with sour milk, lactic acid or citric acid. It shall not contain more than 70.0 per cent moisture and the milk fat content shall not be less than 50.0 per cent on dry matter [1].

The present venture is an innovation in the domain of sweet industry in India. The basic objective is to induct the medicinal property of mint in the human system through rasgulla, which is the preferred sweet of Indians. Mint has a number of medicinal properties. The leaf of mint is used internally as an antispasmodic and to treat irritable bowel syndrome and inflammation of the oral mucosa.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Analysis of mint leaf

Fresh leaves of mint were collected from Madhyamgram region of North 24 Paraganas district in West Bengal from different patches and dried overnight at 60°C. The dried leaf samples were grinded by mortar pastel and protein content was measured by Lowry's method using spectrophotometer as per the standard procedure (Lowry *et al.*, 1951) [2]. The total carbohydrate content was estimated by phenol sulphuric acid method using D-Glucose as standard (Dubois *et al.*, 1956) [3] The total fat in the leaf sample was estimated by Soxhelt method using petroleum ether (80°C) as per the procedure (AOAC, 2000) [4]. Minerals like Ca, K and Mg were analysed as per the standard method of flame photometry.

2.2. Preparation of mint leaf extract

The collected mint leaves were dried and powdered. The dried leaf dusts were soaked overnight in sterilized water and filtered through fine loin cloth. The filtrate was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 20 minutes using a REMI cold centrifuge. The supernatant, thus obtained, was filtered through loin cloth and the collected filtrate was preserved at -20°C in clean TARSON bottles.

2.3. Preparation of rasgulla with mint extract

Rasgulla is prepared from soft and freshly made channa. Cow milk is preferred for the production of rasgulla because it gives soft, spongy and juicy product.

For rasgulla production, channa is kneaded into smooth paste and then small balls of about 15-20 mm diameter and 10-15 grams in weigh are made. The surface of balls should be smooth and free

from of any cracks. One (1) kg of channa yields about 40-60 rasgullas (depending on the size of the rasgulla). Rasgulla balls are cooked in sugar syrup having 50-60 percent sugar concentration for about 15-20 minutes. During cooking, a small amount of water is continuously added to maintain sugar concentration. This make up for the loss of water due to evaporation. About 10 percent of cooking solution is replaced by fresh one, every time it is reused to cook another batch or rasgulla. After cooking rasgulla, balls are soaked in 40-45 percent sugar syrup for about 7-8 hours (Pramanick *et al.*, 2017) [5]. Our specially formulated rasgulla replaced the water of sugar syrup with mint leaf extract and mixed with equivalent proportion of sugar as that of normal (control). The entire marketing of this formulated rasgulla was done by Satyanarayan Mistanna Bhandar, Singur, Hooghly district, West Bengal, India, Figure (1).

Figure 1. Preparation of rasgulla from mint extract at Satyanarayan Mistanna Bhandar, Singur, Hooghly district, West Bengal (India).

Source: Pramanick *et al.*, 2017. [5]

2.4. Analysis of rasgulla (a comparative analysis of control and experimental samples)

The success of any experimental approach is monitored on the basis of a comparative study between control and experimental samples in terms of few parameters (variables) that are relevant indicators of human health. In the present programme, we have used the values of protein, carbohydrate, fat, K, Ca and Mg as indicators of comparative study. These indicators (compounds/elements) are intricately related to human health. [5-7]

3. Results

The proximate composition of the leaves of mint is shown in Figure (2). The level of total carbohydrate is highest 89.26% (dry weight basis) followed by total protein 2.19% (dry weight basis), and total fat 0.50% (dry weight basis).

Figure 2. Proximate composition of mint leaves.

Source: Authors.

The leaves of the species are also the good sources of minerals like K (23.0 mg/g), Ca (5.25 mg/g) and Mg (4.15 mg/g).

Figure 3. Mineral composition of mint leaves.

Source: Authors.

Figures (3), (4) and (5) reflect the mineral composition of mint leaves, control rasgulla and experimental rasgulla (prepared from mint) respectively.

Figure 4. Mineral composition of control rasgulla.

Source: Authors.

Figure 5. Mineral composition of experimental rasgulla (prepared from mint).

Source: Authors.

4. Discussion

Carbohydrate is the basic source of energy, providing 4 Kcal/g (energy/g). The total carbohydrate in mint leaves is very high (89.26%), due to which the mint based rasgulla exhibits high percentage of carbohydrate (51.33%) compared to total carbohydrate in the control rasgulla (48.34%).

Protein is an important biochemical constituents of living organisms. It is responsible for the formation of bones, teeth, hair and the outer layer of skin. It is observed from the result that protein is very low in the mint leaves. This is reflected in the experimental rasgulla prepared from mint in

which the protein contain in 1.90% compared to controlled rasgulla with 4.45% protein content.

The total fat content is extremely low in the mint leaves (0.50%). However, it is seen that in mint based rasgulla the total fat is 1.80% which is attributed to considerable fat content in the control rasgulla (4.97%).

The mineral composition of mint leaves and rasgulla is presented in Figure (3). Potassium (K) is necessary for several vital functions in the organisms. Diets rich in K can reduce the risk of hyper-tension and prevent the possibility of stroke. In the present study the K content of the mint leaves is quite high (23.0 mg/g), due to which, the rasgulla prepared from mint leaves exhibit high K level (19.7 mg/g) compared to control rasgulla (5.97 mg/g).

Caesium (Ca) is an important component of a healthy diet and plays an important role in building strong and dense bones and teeth both in the early and later stages in life. The Ca content in mint leaves is very low (5.25 mg/g), due to which, the value of the element is also low in the rasgulla prepared from mint (3.67 mg/g) compared to the control one (2.80 mg/g).

Magnesium (Mg) is essential to all living cell, where they play a major role in the functioning of important biological polyphosphate compounds like ATP, DNA and RNA. The present research shows that leaves of mint content is very less amount of Mg (4.15 mg/g), due to which the level of the element is Below detectable Level in the rasgulla prepared from mint (1.09 mg/g) and control (0.99 mg/g). Considering the biochemical composition and mineral content of the end product (rasgulla prepared from mint leaves), it can be stated that this can be a unique source of minerals to human beings. The level of K being high in the mint based rasgulla may serve as medicinal desert for hypertensive patient since K reduces blood pressure.

5. Conclusion

Mint, commonly known as ‘Pudina’ in most Indian languages, belongs to the genus *Mentha* in the family Labiatae (Lamiaceae) that includes other commonly grown oil yielding plants such as basil, sage, rosemary, marjoram, lavender and thyme. There are 25–30 species within the genus *Mentha*, including spearmint, peppermint, wild mint, corn mint, curled mint, bergamot, American

mint, Korean mint, etc. of which spearmint is the most common of all. It grows abundantly to 1 ft high, in extensive masses in wet places, riverbank, and marshy areas. It is well distinguished by its downy foliage and whorls of lilac flowers, which are crowded into globose heads towards the summit of the stem. The mint leaves have considerable mineral levels (particularly potassium) and hence the sweets prepared from the leaf extract may be useful to combat hypertension in people.

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